

**ANALYSIS OF THE WORLD PRACTICE AND EXPERIENCE OF
UZBEKISTAN IN RESTORATION OF ARCHITECTURAL OBJECTS OF
THE XX CENTURY**

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Annotation: The article provides an analysis of the methods used in the world practice of restoring the architecture of the twentieth century and a general analysis of the achievements and shortcomings of restoration work in Uzbekistan. Today, restoration, renovation and improvement, in a word, modernization is taking place in all our historical cities. Such work further increases the tourism potential of our country and increases the number of tourists. Finding a balance between historical and modern buildings is one of the most urgent problems of adapting a historical city to modern ones. Examples of unique examples of modernist architecture in the city of Tashkent were presented, their role in the image of the city was discussed.

Аннотация: В статье приводится анализ методов, применяемых в мировой практике реставрации архитектуры XX века и общий анализ достижений и недостатков реставрационных работ в Узбекистане. Сегодня во всех наших исторических городах происходит реставрация, обновление и благоустройство, словом, модернизация. Такая работа еще больше увеличивает туристический потенциал нашей страны и увеличивает количество туристов. Нахождение баланса между исторической и современной застройкой является одной из наиболее актуальных проблем адаптации исторического города к современным. Были представлены примеры уникальных образцов модернистской архитектуры в городе Ташкенте, обсуждена их роль в образе города.

In the space of urban planning and architecture, the concept of reconstruction can cover many aspects, such as innovative design, efficient use of space, sustainability, preservation of historical heritage and others. Architects and urban planners can use the concept of refurbishment to renovate urban landscapes, improve the energy efficiency and sustainability of buildings, create new centers of culture or business, and many other projects.

The renovation approach can be conservative, retaining much of the original building, or radically new, tearing down and completely rebuilding the home. In any case, the goal of the reconstruction concept is to improve the quality of life of people, create attractive urban spaces and preserve the historical or cultural heritage.

Currently, there are a number of tasks to preserve and enrich the historical environment during the restoration and improvement of historical cities. These include the harmonization of historical and modern buildings, the correct solution of historical centers where the most important buildings are located, the definition of the protected zone of monuments, their adaptation to a new function, the repair of engineering networks, road infrastructure, and more. Actual trends in the formation and development of historical cities and their centers, what principles should be based on the implementation of their reconstruction and improvement, as well as the development of the most optimal ways of adapting historical cities to modern requirements [1].

Reconstruction of architectural objects of the 20th century is the process of restoring and recreating buildings created in the 20th century, while preserving their historical and architectural characteristics. The purpose of the reconstruction of such buildings is to preserve and restore them in accordance with the original design and functionality, taking into account modern standards and requirements.

Reconstruction helps to preserve the historical heritage and cultural value of old buildings, and also ensures their functional use in modern conditions. Architectural objects of the 20th century are often popular places for tourists and

are of cultural value for everyone. Renovation of 19th century buildings can be a complex and time-consuming project, but can bring enormous benefits to the historical heritage of cities and society as a whole.

The architecture of Tashkent in the 20th century is notable for significant changes in the style and technology of construction, caused by political, social and economic changes in Uzbekistan. During the 20th century, there were many renovations and new building projects that reflected the influence of modern and Western architectural trends.

The architecture of Tashkent in the 20th century combines various styles and trends, including Soviet, classical, modernism and Western. This reflects the diversity of cultures and history of the city and makes it one of the most interesting and unique cities in Central Asia.

The world practice of restoration of architectural objects of the 20th century covers a variety of methods and approaches that depend on the type of object, its historical and cultural significance, condition and technical capabilities for restoration.

One of the most common methods is to preserve the property in its original form using authentic materials and construction methods. This is an approach often used to preserve significant buildings in the US and Europe, such as US National Park in Jackson Hole, Wyoming. Authentic materials and original construction methods have been used here to preserve buildings that have become icons of American Golden Age architecture.

Another method that is often used in the restoration of architectural objects of the twentieth century is the preservation of the appearance of the object, but the restructuring of its internal structure and the use of modern materials and technologies. This method allows you to keep the appearance of the object, but improve its functionality and use. Examples of such objects are the buildings of museums and exhibition halls such as the Hans Arp Museum in Rollingen, Switzerland (Figure 1). Here the appearance of the building was preserved, but the

internal structure was completely replaced, and modern technologies and materials appeared in the building (Figure 1-2) [2].

There is also a method of preserving an object as a historical memento without attempting to restore its original appearance. Instead, the object is preserved as a "trace of the past" and is used for educational and historical memory purposes. For such objects, interactive museums or exhibitions are created that allow visitors to see how the object looked in the past and how it was used. For example, the BMW World exhibition complex in Munich, Germany. The historic BMW factory buildings of the original look are preserved here, but the interior

Figure 1-3. Museum - Hans Arpa. Rollingen, Switzerland

space has been completely rebuilt and used as an interactive museum to show the history of the automotive industry.

In general, the world practice of restoration of architectural objects of the twentieth century seeks to preserve the heritage of architecture, but at the same time take into account modern technologies and needs. Restoration must be carried out in accordance with international standards and recommendations, such as the charter of the Venice Commission, in order to preserve the objects as cultural and historical assets for future generations.

Uzbekistan has a rich history and cultural heritage, which traditionally covers periods of state formations, artistic movements and famous architectural structures. To preserve and restore cultural heritage objects, various restoration styles and schools are used in Uzbekistan. Specialists-restorers in Uzbekistan use various methods of reconstruction, which include:

Traditional methods: Restorers in Uzbekistan often use traditional building methods to reconstruct historical structures. These methods may include mud brick construction, wood joinery, and ceramic tile work. The use of these methods helps to ensure that the reconstructed structure is as close to the original as possible.

Computer Modeling: In some cases, restoration professionals may use computer modeling to create a 3D model of the original structure. This allows them to better understand the structure and determine the best methods of reconstruction.

Material Analysis: Restoration professionals can also analyze the original materials used in a construction to determine which materials are best used for a reconstruction. This may include the use of spectroscopy, microscopy, or other methods to determine the composition of starting materials.

Replication: Restorers can use replication techniques to create new elements that match the original structure. For example, if a design is missing a decorative element such as ceramic tile, restoration professionals can use traditional methods to create new tiles to match the original design.

Preservation: Conservators in Uzbekistan attach great importance to the preservation of original materials and design of historical buildings. When renovating a structure, they place great emphasis on preserving as much of the original materials and design as possible, and ensuring that the structure complies with current safety and building codes.

From 1979 to the 1990s, the only in Central Asia Uzbek Research Design Institute for the Restoration of Architectural Monuments (UzNIPI Restoration) successfully operated in Tashkent, where more than 300 highly professional specialists developed projects for the restoration, conservation and adaptation of monuments and their protected zones, in a chemical laboratory revealed the compositions of ancient building and decorative materials. The closure of the institute brought significant damage to this area [3].

In recent years, a number of shortcomings and gross errors have been noticed in the restoration of ancient architectural objects. Since such mistakes lead to the loss of valuable monuments and the view of the city, the issues of restoration and preservation of architectural objects were studied and a number of decisions were made.

Heritage protection specialist, research director of the Institute of Modernism, Associate Professor of the Moscow School of Architecture Anna Bronovitskaya, having visited Tashkent, expressed her opinion about the threat of loss to the architecture of the modernist period, attitude towards it and changes in the appearance of the city. In her opinion, “the city is developing very quickly and this development is not accompanied by a program that would protect the valuable heritage of Tashkent. Local specialists did not conduct a detailed survey of historical buildings, so today we are witnessing a rapid loss of valuables. It is especially disappointing when this happens not even as a result of demolitions, but after poor restoration - the buildings lose their appearance, their architectural and cultural value” [4].

A positive example of Soviet architecture, for example, is the well-preserved hotel "Uzbekistan". As you know, it will soon be reconstructed, while, according to the terms of the transaction, the new owner does not have the right to make changes to the appearance. In general, it should be noted that the building has been preserved in a very good condition, and it will stand still for a very, very long time (Figure 4).

It should also be noted about the UzBUM paper mill, which was abandoned for many years after bankruptcy (Figure 4). Recently, the factory has received a new manager, who is now preparing the concept of reconstruction. According to the plans, the former territory of the paper mill will be used as an art business cluster, that is, galleries, a contemporary art center, concert halls, restaurants, etc. will open there. The launch of the project will certainly increase the attractiveness of the entire area, and land and real estate around the art cluster will rise in price

significantly (for example, after the commissioning of one of the largest shopping centers in the capital, Samarqand Darvoza, real estate and office space have risen in price noticeably). It should be noted that the factory workshops built before the revolution of 1917 are basically strong and interesting from an architectural point of view.

A valuable example of architecture in the city center, the Navoi Opera and Ballet Theater is a modernist building that was built in the 1940s, the theater has been preserved in good condition, a big event for the theater in recent years has been the long-awaited reconstruction of the theater, which lasted more than 5 years and completed in October 2015 [5].

The city of Tashkent is rich not only in historical public buildings, but also in residential buildings with a unique design, which greatly contribute to the image of the city. From residential buildings - a completely unique gallery experimental 16-storey residential building "Zhemchug", built of monolithic reinforced concrete in the 80s. There is a house with a similar solution in Madrid. Features of the house are rounded corners and the presence of a large space inside the house, designed for residents to relax. The principle that was programmed as a vertical mahalla really works there.

We must admit that in Tashkent residential buildings of the 60-80s are

Figure 5. Tashkent. Hotel "Uzbekistan".1988

Figure 4. Paper mill (UzBUM)

Figure 5. Tashkent. Residential buildings on Friendship of Peoples Square. 1988

more interesting and diverse. This is partly the result of the high seismicity in Uzbekistan, and specialists at that time already understood that it was impossible to simply replicate typical series here. Therefore, a slightly more generous budget was set for the capital of Uzbekistan (Figure 5). In addition, it was necessary to take into account the local climate. Since household air conditioners were not widely used at that time, the task was to create conditions for natural ventilation, that is, to distribute the chiaroscuro of the facades so that overheating did not occur. As a result, many buildings adapted to local conditions were built in Tashkent, many of which are interestingly executed. For example, the projects of the architect Kosinsky, which can be seen along the street from Nukus to the international airport.

For Tashkent, everything old that has been preserved so far is a huge resource that, with the right approach, can decorate the city and attract tourists. It is important that the city, changing its structure, protect iconic monuments.

Conclusion. In general, the reconstruction of architectural objects of the 20th century in Uzbekistan reflects the diversity of the country's architectural heritage and the importance of preserving its history for future generations. In recent years, significant reconstruction work has been carried out in Tashkent in order to restore and preserve its architectural heritage. The city's efforts are commendable, with attention paid to various historic buildings and structures to ensure their longevity.

The renovation work in Tashkent has helped preserve the city's rich cultural history and showcase the unique architectural styles that have evolved over the centuries. It also contributed to the overall modernization and development of the city.

However, there have been some criticisms of the reconstruction efforts, with concerns about the authenticity of some of the restored buildings and the potential loss of the city's original character. In addition, there were some concerns about the displacement of residents and the impact of the redevelopment on the social fabric of the city.

Despite these difficulties, the reconstruction work in Tashkent undoubtedly contributed to the revival of the city and the preservation of its architectural heritage. As the city continues to develop, it will be important to strike a balance between modernization and preservation in order for Tashkent to retain its unique identity and cultural significance.

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